

RESEARCH CAPABILITY OF INSTRUCTORS AND PROFESSORS IN THE PRIVATE HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS (HEIS) IN THE PHILIPPINES: A CORRELATIONAL STUDY

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Research Capability of Instructors and Professors in the Private Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) in the Philippines: A Correlational Study

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Abstract

Research capability among educators This study determined the research capability of the University of the Visayas college instructors, whose technical knowledge in conducting and publishing scholarly-made articles was assessed, which will enhance the existing research management plan. It identified the demographic profile, research exposure, and capability of the respondents. The works of the literature focused more on teachers' capability in different disciplines however, limited studies have been performed in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This study answered this gap in the literature by assessing the research capability of college instructors and professors at the University of the Visayas-Main Campus. This study used a descriptive-correlational research design with 40 respondents chosen through a sampling technique. Simple Frequency Counts, Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation, and Pearson-r are statistical tools used in this study. The respondents are aware of how to uphold ethical considerations in conducting research (3.28). Most of the instructors are having problems with analyzing data using SPSS, Excel, Minitab, NVivo-QSR, and other software. All other indicators in the demographic profile are not significant to research capability. Research output completed (0.02), research output published internationally (0.03), and citations (0.03) established a significant relationship to research capability. With this, the university research department should make programs that can increase the motivation of instructors to complete their research, and have it published internationally with the chance for the article to be cited so that the level of research capability of the instructors will increase.

Keywords: *research capability, university instructors and professors, descriptive-correlational study, research enhancement program*

Introduction

Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) mandate that conducting research is pivotal to formulating knowledge and having these new insights shared through research publication and presentation, making innovations, especially inside the classroom, and addressing the most pressing issues in society. This is aggrandized by making research one of the core functions of the university, together with instruction, extension, and production (De La Cruz, 2016). The importance of conducting research underscores the fact that instruction, extension, and production should be anchored by research-based data (Cross, 2023). Hence, the college Instructors and Professors should have the necessary skills to conduct research, as this may compromise the rest of the core functions. It is expedient to conduct a research capability assessment to diagnose the different challenges that overshadowed the college instructors and professors from conducting, presenting, and publishing research articles (Cabello, 2022). In the literature, limited studies are conducted at the tertiary level in terms of research capability assessment, which this study is prompted to be facilitated to serve its meaning and purpose (Tolentino, 2021).

The Commission on Higher Education (CHED) surveyed how teachers value the importance of research and their capacity to make scholarly-made research articles. According to Perez et al. (2022), it was found that most of the respondents from Luzon shared that research was given poor priority with limited funding. However, funding is always a problem concerning research, especially in publishing it to Scopus-Indexed journals having expensive Article Processing Fees (APF). Reiterating the study of Wong (2019), as cited by Perez et al., with 92.95% of members of the faculty who joined the development activities in research and publication, only 22.81% were actively involved in the conduct of research. This data is alarming as it does not even reach 50% of the total number of respondents. These activities lasted for two decades. Commonly, some of the teachers who are attending seminars and workshops in research are just there to have their attendance counted and wait for the awarding of certificates. The essence of appreciating the nature of the activity was no longer part of their agenda.

Conducting research and publication is not everyone's cup of tea. Most of the teachers have doubts about how they can finish doing it, especially without proper guidance from the experts in field research (Carter et al., 2021; Donmez et al., 2023). Aside from the intrinsic reasons, most of the instructors and professors are having problems with the right methodologies, correct statistical treatment, and even the data gathering procedure (Perez et al., 2022; Tatto, 2023). These challenges can be augmented when there is a research clinic purposely to provide tailored-fit training to what are the needs of the instructors and professors (Uflewski et al., 2024; Bongco et al., 2023). Research capability assessment determines the level of research exposure and the knowledge and expertise of the instructors and professors in the conduct of research. It is in this process that they get the help they need. As defined by Salom et al. (2013), research capability is the ability to identify the answers to the problems encountered by the individual following the scientific process of planning, especially the nature of the study, its structure, and what picture can be depicted as to how it will be understood by the

readers, the gathering of the pertinent data, and the interpretation of the what appropriate statistical tools can be used to treat the data gathered.

The need to conduct this study is timely. Aside from the ranking of universities, the quality of instruction to be delivered inside the classroom should be the main motivation why research should be conducted. Research capability assessment can be of great help to instructors and professors in embracing the biggest room in this world – the room for improvement (Bonganciso, 2024; Salde & Mamaoag, 2021). Knowing their learning gaps can be supported by a management plan. Improving research culture within the university is not an overnight task that can be completed right away (Chen, 2024; Vasquez et al., 2022). It is a journey of uncovering new ideas, insights, and innovations which will never end. When instructors are capacitated to conduct research, it creates a domino effect on all learners and even on the community where the university is situated (Gonzales et al., 2020; Liwanag et al., 2023). It will all start with how the university administration capacitates the instructors and professors by encouraging them to have more exposure and training. This is more like an investment because when the time comes that the teachers are already experts, they are the ones who will bring more opportunities to the university.

The University of the Visayas is composed of eight campuses with a laboratory school. This study centers on the main campus instructors and professors. With the vision of the university to be a center of excellence that inspires faith in the Almighty, love, leadership, and service to humanity, the conduct of research is a very important task to do in materializing this vision. To be a center of excellence, providing excellent instruction with meaningful learning experiences should be observed and sustained. This study is a necessity to know the root causes of why research and publication is still one of the most challenging tasks among instructors and professors despite the incentives and motivational programs that the university is offering. The findings of this study can benefit not just the university but the instructors and professors themselves – their personal and professional growth and development through research and publication. The enhanced management plan can scaffold them to increase their research capability and technical knowledge on research publication.

Research Questions

This study determined the research capability of the University of the Visayas college instructors, whose technical knowledge in conducting and publishing scholarly-made articles was assessed, which will enhance the existing research management plan. Specifically, this study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 age;
 - 1.2 gender;
 - 1.3 marital status;
 - 1.4 academic position/faculty ranking;
 - 1.5 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.6 number of years in service?
2. What is the respondent's level of research exposure in terms of:
 - 2.1 number of years in conducting research; and
 - 2.2 number of research outputs as to:
 - 2.2.1 completed;
 - 2.2.2 presented;
 - 2.2.2.1 local;
 - 2.2.2.2 regional;
 - 2.2.2.3 national; and
 - 2.2.2.4 international?
 - 2.2.3 Published
 - 2.2.3.1 national;
 - 2.2.3.2 international
 - 2.3 Number of Citations as to
 - 2.3.1 h-index; and
 - 2.3.2 i10-index?
 - 2.4 Research Seminars, Training, and Conferences attended
 - 2.4.1 local;
 - 2.4.2 regional;
 - 2.4.3 national; and
 - 2.4.4 international?
3. What is the level of research capability among the college instructors and professors of the University of the Visayas?
4. What is the significant relationship between the respondent's demographic profile, research exposure, and capability?
5. What enhanced management plan can be crafted based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design. This design is appropriate for establishing the significant relationship between a dependent variable (research capability) and the independent variables (demographic profile and research exposure). The respondents of this study are the college instructors and professors at the University of the Visayas – Main Campus. They were selected through a simple random sampling. A total of 40 instructors and professors volunteered to participate in the study.

Instruments

An adapted instrument from the study of Perez et al. (2022) was used in gathering the data. The instrument has a good score of 0.89 in its Cronbach's alpha for the reliability testing and was validated according to Colton and Covert (2007) cited by Cabello and Bonotan (2021). The instrument has three parts, namely, (1) demographic profile, (2) research exposure, and (3) research capability questionnaire. The first part is composed of name (optional), age, gender, marital status, academic position/faculty ranking, highest educational attainment, and number of years in service. The second part is composed of the respondent's research exposure, which is the number of years in conducting research, the number of research outputs as completed, presented, and published, and the number of Citations as to h-index and i10-index. The third part is the research capability questionnaire with a 4-point Likert Scale, which is composed of not capable (1.00-1.80), less capable (1.81-2.60), capable (2.61-3.20), and very capable (3.21-4.00).

Procedure

The researchers crafted a letter to be approved by the authorities. After having the letter approved, the researchers coordinated with the different Deans in the different colleges to have the questionnaires administered. Along with the instrument is the letter to explain the nature and purpose of the research and ask permission to collect data from the respondents. The respondents are neither forced nor coerced into participating in the research study following the research standards and ethics. After the gathering of the data, the researchers used statistical tools to treat the data.

Statistical Analysis

This study utilized the simple count and frequency for the respondent's demographic profile. The mean and standard deviation will be used for the research capability of the respondents. Pearson r will be utilized for establishing the significant relationship between the dependent and independent variables.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data in tabular form with discussion, interpretation, and implication with corroboration of the literature. The arrangement of the tables answers the research questions respectively.

This table shows the demographic profile of the respondents elaborately presenting the frequency of gender, age, marital status, academic position, highest educational attainment, number of years in service, and number of years in conducting research. This provides a substantial discussion in understanding the variables. In this table, it can be gleaned that 62.50% (25 counts) of the respondents were female and 37.50% (15 counts) were male. Moreover, most of the respondents were 26-35 years old with 45.00% (18 counts) and most of them were single with 75.00% (30 counts). Out of the 40 respondents, 95.00% with 38 counts were Instructor I-III and 22 (55.00%) of them were continuing with their master's degree. Furthermore, the table evidently shows that the majority of the respondents with 26 counts (65.00%) having a tenure year of 3 years and below an experience in conducting of years of 3 years and below.

Table 1. *Demographic Profile*

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Male	15	37.50
Female	25	62.50
<i>Age</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
25 and below	13	32.50
26-35	18	45.00
36-45	4	10.00
46 and above	5	12.50
<i>Marital Status</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Single	30	75.00
Married	10	25.00
Widow	0	0.00
Annulled	0	0.00
<i>Academic Position</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Instructor I-III	38	95.00

Assistant Professor I-IV	1	2.50
Associate Professor I-V	1	2.50
Professor I-VI	0	0.00
<i>Highest Educational Attainment</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Bachelor's Degree	7	17.50
With Masters Units	22	55.00
Full Fledged Masters	8	20.00
With Doctoral Units	0	0.00
Full Fledged Doctors	3	7.50
<i>Number of Years in Service</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
3 years and below	26	65.00
4 to 9 years	7	17.50
10 to 15 years	3	7.50
16 to 21 years	2	5.00
22 and above	2	5.00
<i>Number of Years in Conducting Research</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
3 years and below	30	75.00
4 to 9 years	9	22.50
10 to 15 years	0	0.00
16 to 21 years	1	2.50
22 and above	0	0.00
Total	40	100

With the data presented above, it can be implied that in the education realm, there are more female teachers than male ones because of the multifaceted factors, including historical and cultural perspectives. The perception that this profession requires stability of emotional state radiates to the capacity of female individuals to handle these requirements (O'Meara, 2016). It can also be elicited above that the faculties of the University of Visayas – College of Arts and Sciences (UV-CAS) were in the age group of adults, but they were newly-hired teachers as they are on the first level of their academic rank with minimal teaching experience, master’s unit, and drastically low rate of experience in conducting research in the said institution or even in their teaching journey. Also, this table implies that most of the faculties had no family obligations, as a huge number of them were single. With this, it can be concluded that the UV-CAS has a huge potential in pursuing their research journey as they are still capacitated to do so based on their age and academic development. Also, the fact that they are still in their first phase of teaching experience in the institution provides them with a wide array of opportunities to work on their research experience. With appropriate activities to be conducted internally and externally, the faculties may elevate their capacity in terms of conducting and publishing research (Saroyan & Frenay, 2023).

Table 2.1 Research Exposure in Output Presentation

Output Presentation	Research Output (Completed)		ROP Local		ROP Regional		ROP National		ROP International	
	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P	F	P
3 articles and below	35	87.50	35	87.50	37	92.50	36	90.00	36	90.00
4 to 9 articles	4	10.00	4	10.00	3	7.50	3	7.50	3	7.50
10 to 15 articles	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0	0	0.00	0	0.00
16 to 21 articles	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0	1	2.50	1	2.50
22 articles and above	1	2.50	1	2.50	0	0	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	40	100	40	100	40	100	40	100	40	100

Legend: ROP = Research Output Presentation F = Frequency P = Percentage

Table 2.1 presents the acquired data from the respondents in terms of the research exposure in output presentation. It can be seen that the respondents of 35 out of 40 (87.50%) completed only 3 articles and below, which is quite low for a faculty in a higher education institution. Also, it can be seen from above that 35 faculties (87.50%) only presented 3 articles and below in the local research colloquium. With the same number of articles, 37 faculties (92.50%) presented their research output in a regional setup, 36 faculties (90.00%) exposed their output in the national research activities, and 36 faculties (90.00) shared their research in the international arena.

Table 2.2 displays the data about the respondents’ research output in terms of its completion and national, and international publication. It can be deciphered that 87.50% of the total population completed only 3 articles and below that were subject for publication, only 4 with a percentage of 10.00% published 4 articles to 9 articles, no frequency for both 10-15 and 16-21 and lastly, there were only 2.50% with a frequency of 1 count who completed 22 articles and above. In terms of publication in the existing journals in the country, a large percentage belongs to the least range which is 3 articles and below with 37 counts out of 40 respondents (92.50%) and the lowest percentage comes from 10-15 articles and 22 articles and above with both 0 frequencies 0.00%). Also, it can be gleaned that the range 3 articles and below got the highest frequency of 36 counts (90.00) while the 4-9 articles range got the lowest one with no frequency in terms of respondents’ output published in an internationally acclaimed journal. Considering these numbers, it can be implicated that

the production rate of the faculties in terms of publishing articles is evidently low which can be construed as decreasing the quality of the academic reputation of the institution that these faculties are working with. This is because the visibility of these faculties in this area in a global arena is drastically low with limited contribution to the pool of knowledge which has a direct impact on its ranking. Moreover, it may be considered disadvantageous to the institution’s culture in research and innovation as it seems weak considering the presented above.

Table 2.2 *Research Exposure in Output Citation*

Citations	Number of Citations		h-index Citations		i10 h-index Citations	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
10 and below	36	90.00	36	90.00	36	90.00
11 to 30 counts	0	0.00	0	0.00	1	2.50
31 to 60 counts	2	5.00	2	5.00	2	5.00
61 to 90 counts	1	2.50	1	2.50	1	2.50
91 to 120 counts	1	2.50	1	2.50	0	0.00
121 to 150 counts	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
151 and above	0	0.00	0	0.00	0	0.00
Total	40	100	40	100	40	100

Table 2.3 shows the elicited data from the respondents’ research exposure in terms of the citations both the h-index and i10 h-index they received from the published articles. The table presented the highest frequency of 36 with a percentage of 90.00% coming from the 10 and below range which is the least range in terms of its count while the lowest frequency of 0 (0.00%) deciphered from 11 to 30 counts, 121 to 150 counts, and 151 and above ranges. This data elicited from the respondents’ number of citations for all their published articles. Furthermore, it can also be seen that the same range got the highest frequency and percentage of respondents’ h-index citations and i10 h-index citations with 36 counts and 90.00% respectively. Meanwhile, the same ranges also got the lowest frequency and counts for both h-index and i10 h-index citations. With this, it can be implied that these numbers were parallel to the number of outputs being published both internationally and nationally, which may also affect the faculty’s visibility as research scientists in the global ranking. This ranking is vital in putting the institution’s name to the myriads of world recognition as an educational institution providing 21st-century education to its stakeholders.

Table 2.3. *Research Exposure in Output Citation*

Output Publication	Research Output (Completed)		Research Publication National		Research Publication International	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
3 articles and below	35	87.50	37	92.50	36	90.00
4 to 9 articles	4	10.00	2	5.00	0	0.00
10 to 15 articles	0	0.00	0	0.00	2	5.00
16 to 21 articles	0	0.00	1	2.50	1	2.50
22 articles and above	1	2.50	0	0	1	2.50
Total	40	100	40	100	40	100

With the number of faculties in line with their research output completion, presentation experience, publication, and number of citations, it can be implicated that UV-CAS faculties currently have a few research exposures based on the HEI’s research intended goals for instructors. This may be considered a huge gap as it does not align to 21st century education which centers on research and innovation and may impact the quality of education that these instructors are giving to their students. According to the study of Bowman et al. (2022), engaging in professional development activities such as conducting research and producing innovation provides opportunities to revolutionize current skills and knowledge parallel to global trends and needs. The experience that they can get from it, especially if they are targeting educational gaps, would reconstruct their way of delivering education to the students, which is vital for their growth and development. With this, it is in great urgency that these faculties should reconsider acting upon the goals set for them – to expose themselves more to research presentations, publications, citations, and innovations.

Table 3. *Level of Research Capability*

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
I know well the Nature of Educational Research.	3.00	0.68	Capable
I can understand the language of Research.	3.10	0.71	Capable
I am familiar with the famous authors in research books.	2.78	0.62	Capable
I know how to make a research title.	3.18	0.64	Capable
I know how to write an introduction to an article.	3.25	0.63	Very Capable
I know how to look for Literature and Studies.	3.20	0.69	Capable
I know how to write a review of related literature.	3.25	0.67	Very Capable
I know how to formulate research question/s.	2.93	0.69	Capable
I know how to set the parameters of the study.	2.98	0.66	Capable
I know how to make conceptual and theoretical frameworks.	3.08	0.57	Capable
I can decide what appropriate research design I need to use in my study.	3.03	0.66	Capable

I know the kind of sampling technique I need to utilize.	3.03	0.73	Capable
I know what is population and sample.	3.15	0.74	Capable
I can identify a particular statistical tool to be used in my study.	2.90	0.67	Capable
I know how to validate an instrument and have it tested its reliability.	2.78	0.80	Capable
I know how to sustain trustworthiness of the data gathered.	2.98	0.73	Capable
I know how to conduct interview both individually and through FGD.	2.95	0.55	Capable
I know what are the ethical considerations in conducting research.	3.28	0.64	Very Capable
I know how to analyze results.	3.00	0.68	Capable
I know how to read tables and other graphical representations of data.	3.00	0.78	Capable
I know how to use SPSS, Excel, Minitab, NVivo-QSR and other software in analyzing the data for both Qualitative and Quantitative researches.	2.73	0.82	Capable
I know how to corroborate the results through anchoring the works of literature and studies.	2.90	0.71	Capable
I know how to make conclusions.	3.13	0.69	Capable
I know to how to do in-text citation.	3.13	0.69	Capable
I know how to paraphrase and summarize.	3.10	0.71	Capable
I know how to use APA 7 th Edition in doing citation.	3.05	0.78	Capable
I know how to make my paper publishable.	2.98	0.80	Capable
I know how to scrutinize journals.	3.00	0.78	Capable
I know how to present my paper in the international conferences.	2.85	0.74	Capable
I am good in making the abstract of the study.	3.08	0.69	Capable

Legend: Least Capable 1.0-1.8; Less Capable 1.81 – 2.60; Capable 2.61 – 3.20; Very Capable 3.21-4.00

Table 3 provides the treated data from the respondents’ responses regarding their research capability. This table evidently shows that the statement “I know what the ethical considerations are in conducting research.” got the highest mean of 3.28 with a standard deviation (SD) of 0.64, which is interpreted as very capable. Meanwhile, the statement “I know how to use SPSS, Excel, Minitab, NVivo-QSR and other software in analyzing the data for both Qualitative and Quantitative research.” got the lowest mean of 2.73 with an SD of 0.82, which has a description of capable. The mean scores of the remaining items were fairly high and interpreted as capable and very capable. With this, it can be implicated that many of the faculties at UV-CAS have the knowledge and skills to conduct research and publish it in different national and international journals.

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Demographic Profile and Research Capability

Variables	n	r value	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Age	40	-0.26	0.10	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Gender	40	0.13	0.43	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Marital Status	40	-0.27	0.89	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Academic Position	40	-0.01	0.97	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Highest Educational Attainment	40	0.08	0.61	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Number of Years in Service	40	-0.19	0.24	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Number of years in conducting research	40	-0.01	0.95	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis

Table 4 presented treated data from the respondents' profile and their research capability tested for its significant relationship. From the data above, it can be deciphered that the highest p-values were the academic position and research capability variables, with 0.97. Meanwhile, the lowest p-value comes from the variables age and research capability, with 0.10. However, both were interpreted as Not Significant. With this, the decision is to accept the null hypothesis. Also, the table evidently showed that all variables under the demographic profile did not show any significant relationship with the respondents’ research capability. This can be implicated in that regardless of age, status in life, position in the institution, attainment in professional development, tenure in work, and research experience, the skills and knowledge in pursuing research will not be impacted by these variables. This can be concretized by the study of Sulaiman and Ismail (2020), in which they found that there was no direct relationship between the demographic profile and research capacity as there were other underlying constructs, such as motivational factors (Zhang et al., 2021) and institutional support (Culver et al., 2020) that surround within the parameters of this concern and interacting with each other which can be a good ground for another inquiry.

Table 5. Significant Relationship between Research Exposure and Research Capability

Variables	n	r value	p-value	Remarks	Decision
Research Output Completed	40	-0.36	0.02	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Presented Locally	40	-0.22	0.17	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Presented Regionally	40	-0.24	0.12	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Presented Nationally	40	-0.20	0.20	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Presented Internationally	40	-0.20	0.20	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Published Nationally	40	-0.13	0.42	Not Significant	Accept the Null Hypothesis
Research Output Published Internationally	40	-0.34	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Number of citations	40	-0.34	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
h-index	40	-0.34	0.03	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis
i10 index	40	-0.26	0.04	Significant	Reject the Null Hypothesis

Table 5 provided treated data testing for the significant relationship between the respondents' research exposure and research capability. It can be gleaned that the Research Output Completed was found to be correlated with the research capacity of the respondents. Also, the variables research output published internationally, number of citations, h-index, and i10 index were found to be correlated with the respondent's research capacity. Meanwhile, the variables Research Output Presented Locally, Regionally, Nationally, Internationally, and Research Output Published in the journal existed in the national arena were tested to be not significant with the respondent's research capacity, meaning there is no underlying relationship, and these variables does not affect the other. With this, the results imply that attending only local and national research workshops and conferences will not increase your capability of producing research. When attending conferences, it should not be for attendance only. Learning insights should be applied and put into action so that the research capability of an individual will be enhanced and practiced.

Conclusion

Research capability is vital in improving and generating knowledge where innovations and progress in one's professional growth are attained. As transpired in this study, citations and research output completed, such as publishing papers internationally, are impactful in increasing the research capability of the instructors. The profile of the respondents is not necessarily a factor in conducting research, as anyone can be a researcher if one has the passion to do it. However, the instructors should be given technical support in the conduct of research wherein observing the ethical considerations is sustained and manipulating statistical tools is honed.

This study highly recommends that the university administration can initiate and facilitate a seminar and workshop series on the use of Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS), Excel, Minitab, NVivo-QSR, and other software in analyzing the data for both Qualitative and Quantitative research. This paves the way to assist instructors in familiarizing these statistical tools in treating the data gathered. The university can also initiate a research clinic where instructors experiencing unique challenges in conducting research will be given support and assistance.

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